

EFFECT ON ZINC DOPED MAGNESIUM AMMONIUM PHOSPHATE (STRUVITE) CRYSTALS BY SPECTRAL ANALYSIS

R. Selvaraju*¹ and A. Sivasakthi^{†2}

^{1,*}Department of Physics (FEAT), Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar, Tamilnadu, India

²Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar, Tamilnadu, India.

Abstract

Urolithiasis is the most common and major stone formation disease found in the human urinary system ever since the early days of civilization till now. Urinary calculi are composed of some insoluble crystalline compounds such as ammonium, calcium and phosphate. Struvite stones cause the majority of urinary calculi problems in women. It consists of a chemical composition of Magnesium Ammonium Phosphate ($\text{MgNH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Zinc is a trace element found in our bodies that supports a variety of activities. The research aims to study the nucleation, aggregation and growth of struvite crystals under the influence of Zinc Chloride. The invitro crystallization of struvite crystals is grown by the single gel diffusion method using a silica gel bed. The impact of Zinc Chloride in the struvite crystals is analyzed by various techniques such as XRD, FT-IR and SEM with EDX. The orthorhombic crystalline structure of struvite and zinc-doped struvite crystals are confirmed through powder XRD. The presence of ammonium (NH), Phosphate (PO) and Metal-Oxygen bonds are identified by FT-IR. The spherical shape of grown crystals and their elementary compositions are determined by SEM with EDX. This data of invitro crystallization contributes to understanding the struvite crystal formation and managing urolithiasis more effectively.

Keywords: Zinc doping, FT-IR, XRD, Struvite, SEM, X-Ray spectrum, diffusion gel growth

1. Introduction

Nephrolithiasis is potentially a fatal condition that affects the urinary system of humans worldwide. The formation of urinary stones is affiliated with the unsaturated Calcium, phosphorus, Oxalate, Purine metabolism and infection in the urinary tract (Chauhan & Joshi 2013; Das 2017). These cause the formation of stones in the site of the kidney, ureter and bladder. Calcium Phosphate, Calcium hydrogen Phosphate, Calcium Oxalate, Uric acid, and L-cystine are major diagenized urinary stones. Among Phosphate, Magnesium hydrogen phosphate trihydrate and Magnesium Ammonium Phosphate Hexahydrate are classified as struvite in mineralogy (Alelign & petros 2018; Manzoor et al., 2018). It is also called urine sand, phosphatic stones, infection stones, triple phosphate stone and urease stones. Struvites are majorly caused by Urinary Tract infections (UTIs) influenced by urolithic bacteria which convert urea into ammonium to make alkaline urine, the phosphate and magnesium are mixed in the urine and linked to infectious urinary stones (Flannigan et al 2018; Schaffer, J. N., & Pearson, 2017). Among the most difficult and painful types of stone illnesses, struvite stones have the potential for life-threatening outcomes form of infection (Raja et al 2019).

Struvite makes up 30% of all human kidney stones and it is heavily influenced by the infectious tract. In contrast, the insoluble trace elements cause of urinary calculi in humans and animals (Polat, S., & Eral, H. B. 2022). The function of human body needs a quite amount of trace compounds such as Mg, Sr, Cr, Mn, Cd, Pb, Zn, Ni, Cu, Co, Au, Ti, Bi, etc., in addition to primary metabolism. (Selvaraju & Bhuvaneshwari 2020; Singh & Rai 2014; Alamani, et al 2021)

Zinc is regarded as a trace element vital to human life, primarily present in muscles (60%) and bones (30%) with skin making up (5%). Healthy growth and development of the human body depend heavily on maintaining an adequate level of Zinc (Zn). Zinc is a very essential trace element and a heavy metal renowned for high anti-oxidant and anti-bacterial activity. Many health issues including immunodeficiency, hypogonadism growth retardation, and neurological and sensory dysfunctions, occur due to zinc deficiency (Shen et al 2024; Fukada et al 2011; Mohsenpour et al 2019). Zinc plays a critical role in maintaining the physiological function of our human body. Infection in the tract is mostly caused by bacteria and zinc possesses high anti-bacterial properties (Barker et al 2020; Kiouri et al 2023).

So, the main objective of this research is to assess the impact of zinc ions in the biomineralization process of struvite crystals by invitro crystallization in a silica gel medium. The growth nucleation aggregation and pH of the gel-grown crystals are analyzed through various techniques. FT-IR spectroscopy is used to analyze the chemical composition of Pure and Zinc influenced struvite crystals. The Microstructure of grown crystals is analyzed by SEM with EDX. Crystalline shape and lattice parameters of invitro-grown crystals are obtained through XRD data.

2. Materials and Method

The Pure and Zinc added struvite crystals are grown in a invitro medium by single gel diffusion gel growth techniques. The gel is prepared by mixing an 0.5 M of Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate ($\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$) aqueous solution with Sodium Metasilicate maintained at a specific gravity of 1.03gm/cm^{-3} . pH level of the gel solution is adjusted by adding glacial

acetic acid to set the pH of 7.5. 20ml of suspension is transferred to a test tube of length 150×25mm diameter it acts as a crystallization vessel to obtain a gel. The suspension is allowed to set after a gelation period of days. The supernatant solution consists 20ml of 0.5M Magnesium acetate tetrahydrate (MgCH_3COO)₂ is added for pure struvite and mixture of 0.5M of Zinc Chloride and Magnesium acetate tetrahydrate of 20ml is added over the set gel for Zinc influenced struvite crystals. The whole experiment is performed under room temperature(37°C). After the gelation period of 1month the pure and zinc doped struvite crystals are harvested prerequisite for the development of crystals are given in below Table. 1. The total mass and total volume of harvested crystals in each test tube are recorded. The Zn Magnesium Ammonium Phosphate crystal reaction are resolved.

Table. 1. The optimum condition for the growth of Zinc doped struvite crystal

S.No	Parameters	Optimum Condition
1	Density of Sodium meta silicate	1.03 gm/cm ⁻³
2	PH of gel	7.5
3	Concentration (MgCH_3COO) ₂	0.5 M
4	Concentration ZnCl_2	0.025 M
5	Concentration of $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$	0.5 M
6	Gel setting period	2 days
7	Gel aging	1 month
8	Period of growth	21 days
9	Temperature	Room Temperature

3. Result and Discussion

The single gel diffusion technique is effective in growing pure and zinc doped struvite crystals. FT-IR, XRD and SEM with EDX are used to analyse the gel grown crystals. In pure struvite crystals, the absorption peak at 1437cm⁻¹ is due to presence of NH_4^+ (ν_4) antisymmetric bending of ammonium whereas 1430 cm⁻¹ in zinc doped struvite. Phosphate, Magnesium, Zinc and metal oxygen bonds absorption peaks are identified by FT-IR analysis. The orthorhombic crystalline nature of pure and zinc impacted struvite with increase peak intensity in (002) and 110 planes are observed with the help of XRD data. Further, the shape and morphology of the grown crystals is analysed by SEM. O, Mg, P and Zn are

present in pure and zinc doped struvite crystals. The atomic percentage and chemical composition are determined by SEM with EDX analysis was reported by (Huang et al 2021; Paun et al 2012; Hutnik et al 2020)

3.1 Fourier Transform- Infrared Spectroscopy analysis

To qualitatively examine the material, the FT-IR spectra are acquired at room temperature using a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer and the KBr pellet method in the wave number range between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} . The FT-IR spectrum of pure and Zn^{2+} doped struvite crystals are depicted in Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b. The experimental data such as wave number and symmetric vibrations of molecules in the grown crystals are shown in Table. 2. FT-IR spectroscopy is successfully applied to analyze the individual characteristic peaks that hold the chemical composition of struvite such as water, ammonium, phosphate, magnesium and zinc. The presence of water crystalline is observed by the absorption peak at 2391 cm^{-1} for pure and it was found to be shifted to 2371 cm^{-1} assigned to water's H-O-H stretching vibration in Zinc influenced struvite. Due to tetrahedron property, NH_4^+ shows four vibration symmetries V_1, V_2, V_3 and V_4 . (Vasuki & Selvaraju 2019) The symmetric stretching vibration of V_1 of ammonium is observed at 2931 cm^{-1} and it changed to 2937 cm^{-1} due to the impact of Zinc, for the V_2 symmetric stretching vibration absorption peak of ammonia (-NH) band at 1645 cm^{-1} which undergoes vibration changes and the peak is observed at 1613 cm^{-1} . The inorganic hydrate compound of N-H shows an antisymmetric stretching peak at 3482 cm^{-1} for a pure and major change in broad peak at 3249 cm^{-1} for zinc doped struvite. There is a minor shift from 1437 cm^{-1} to 1431 cm^{-1} for V_4 symmetric bending for dopant added grown crystals. The presence of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) peaks is absorbed at 891 cm^{-1} and 884 cm^{-1} change in shift is observed which is due to the deformation of -OH linked to Mg^{2+} . Due to the doping effect of Zinc in pure struvite, there is a change in shift at 763 cm^{-1} for pure and 765 cm^{-1} for Zinc. The characteristic absorption peak at 1236 cm^{-1} and 1164 cm^{-1} are shifted to hydrated phosphate under the influence of Zinc by the reported values (Suryawanshi 2021).

Table.2 FT-IR Data for pure and zinc doped struvite crystals

Pure struvite Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Zinc doped struvite Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Vibration band Assignment
3483	3249	H-O-H, N-H stretching vibration of water crystalline
2931	2937	V_1 Symmetric stretching vibration of N-H in NH_4^+ units
2391	2371	H-O-H stretching modes of vibration of a cluster of water molecules of crystallization
1645	1613	V_2 Symmetric bending vibration of N-H in NH_4^+ units
1437	1434	V_4 Asymmetric bending vibration of N-H in NH_4^+ units
1236	1430	Asymmetric stretching vibration of PO_4^{3-} units

1007	1003	V ₃ Asymmetric stretching vibration of PO ₄ ³⁻ units
891	884	V ₁ Symmetric stretching vibration of PO ₄ ³⁻ units deformation of OH linked to Mg ²⁺
763	765	Metal oxygen bonds
571	572	V ₄ Asymmetric bending modes PO ₄ ³⁻
462	461	V ₂ Symmetric bending vibration of PO ₄ ³⁻ units

3.2 X-Ray Diffraction Spectroscopy Analysis

The structure, phase, crystallinity, size and shape of the invitro grown struvite crystals are analyzed using Powder XRD. Using CuK α radiation with a wavelength of 1.5406Å, the study is conducted using a Philips Xpert diffractometer. Powder-X is the computer program used to analyze the data. Fig. 3a and 3b shows the assigned XRD planes of Pure and Zinc doped struvite crystals. Table 3 and Table 4 show the XRD data of controlled and Zinc treated crystals. The hkl values, d spacing and lattice parameter of grown crystals are calculated according to the XRD pattern the grown crystals are crystallized in orthorhombic crystalline nature. The crystalline structure of controlled struvite is not altered under the influence of Zinc but the peaks observed in Zinc doped struvite are slightly shifted due to the phase change of planes which confirms zinc entered in the lattice of the crystal plane. The sharp peaks at (111),(002),(012),(022),planes having a high intensity lead to the crystallization of struvite and it matches very well with the JCPDS No: (77-2303 ,71-2089). The X- ray pattern of Zinc treated struvite crystals also shows a similar nature to controlled structure but not affect the crystalline nature of the sample reported by (Prywer et al 2024 ; Indumathi & Venkatachalam 2019)

Fig 3. X-RAY Spectrum of Pure and Zinc-doped struvite crystals

Table. 3. XRD data for Pure Struvite crystals

Observed value			Standard value			h k l
2θ	I/I _o	d-spacing (Å)	2θ	I/I _o	d-spacing (Å)	
14.86	42	5.96	14.97	38	5.91	101
15.76	80	5.62	15.78	60	5.60	002
16.47	37	5.39	16.44	24	5.38	011
19.01	10	4.69	19.26	4	4.60	110
20.75	100	4.28	20.84	100	4.25	111
21.41	50	4.16	21.43	34	4.14	012
25.66	24	3.47	25.59	9	3.47	200
27.02	33	3.29	27.05	24	3.29	103
29.24	11	3.05	29.49	10	3.02	210
30.48	56	2.93	30.57	44	2.92	211
31.84	46	2.81	31.88	28	2.80	120
33.39	60	2.68	33.23	40	2.69	002
35.73	8	2.51	35.71	5.6	2.51	122
38.20	12	2.35	38.23	9	2.35	213
42.37	8	2.13	42.41	5	2.12	222
43.98	10	2.05	43.98	8	2.05	214
44.04	10	2.03	44.20	2	2.04	030
46.14	14	1.96	46.18	4	1.96	130
50.69	17	1.80	50.60	9	1.80	215
52.60	15	1.73	52.59	11	1.73	133

Table. 4 XRD data for Zinc doped Struvite crystals

Observed value			Standard value			h k l
2θ	I/I _o	d-spacing (Å)	2θ	I/I _o	d-spacing (Å)	
15.05	39	5.86	15.00	46	5.89	101
15.98	65	5.52	15.81	65	5.59	002
16.61	24	5.39	16.45	29	5.38	011
19.39	8	4.59	19.29	3	4.59	110
20.94	100	4.28	20.86	100	4.25	111
21.56	40	4.16	21.46	31	4.13	012
25.79	23	3.47	25.64	9	3.47	200
27.23	31	3.29	27.10	23	3.28	103
29.57	9	3.05	29.54	10	3.02	210
30.65	59	2.93	30.62	44	2.91	211
31.99	40	2.1	31.94	29	2.79	004
33.43	57	2.68	33.26	44	2.69	022
35.91	8	2.51	35.75	5	2.51	122
38.40	10	2.35	38.29	11	2.35	213
42.53	7	2.13	42.47	6	2.12	222
43.89	10	2.05	43.73	2	2.05	024
44.08	10	2.03	44.08	10	2.04	214
46.40	12	1.96	46.34	11	1.96	223
50.85	15	1.80	50.85	11	1.80	215
52.79	11	1.73	52.70	12	1.73	133

3.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy dispersion X-Ray Spectroscopy

The morphology and microstructure of Gel grown controlled and Zinc doped struvite crystals are studied using SEM. Fig.4a and 4b show the micrographs of pure and Zinc treated crystals. Both the samples are spherical in Shape, which seems to influence Zinc and shows no impact on the shape of the struvite. So, the surface morphology of Zinc treated struvite remains unchanged (Suryawanshi 2021). Fig. 5a and 5b show the EDX spectrum. In addition to O, Mg and P the peaks of Zn are also observed in Zinc doped struvite. Zn^{2+} ions incorporated in the samples are confirmed by EDAX. The atomic percentage of pure struvite for O, Mg and P are found to be 57.02%, 16.93% and 26.04% for Zinc doped struvite O, Mg, P and Zn show 56.01%, 14.35%, 22.07% and 4.77%. A decrease in the molar ratio of Magnesium and phosphorus causes the Zn^{2+} ions to react on the growth of crystals and the ammonium in the samples is unpredictable due to its low atomic number (Muryanto & Bayuseno 2014; Zhang, C et al 2018).

Fig. 4 SEM image of Pure and Zinc doped struvite

Fig. 5 EDX spectrum of Pure and Zinc doped Struvite

4. Conclusion

The invitro crystallization of pure and Zinc treated struvite crystals are successfully grown by single gel diffusion method using silica gel the nucleation, aggregation, growth, pH and temperature of the crystals are maintained and treated with Zn^{2+} . The grown pure and Zinc doped crystals are harvested after the gelation period. The harvested crystals consist of phosphate, magnesium, ammonium and zinc confirmed by FT-IR spectroscopy. The shifting of peaks in treated samples is varied from controlled samples due to the doping effect. The shape and dimension of struvite crystals are significantly influenced by the addition of zinc ions during the crystallization process. The XRD analysis shows the grown crystals are in orthorhombic crystalline nature. The pure and zinc added struvite crystals are spherical in structure and this is confirmed with the help of SEM microanalysis. The EDX analysis established the existence of various elements, including Magnesium, Phosphorus, and Zinc. The

addition of Zinc changes the characteristic absorption peaks of the pure struvite crystals but the morphology and crystalline nature of the struvite crystals remain unchanged.

Reference

1. Alamani, B. G., Gale, J. D., & Rimer, J. D. (2021). Zinc ions modify calcium oxalate growth by distinct transformation of crystal surface termination. *Crystal Growth & Design*, 21(6), 3375-3383.
2. Alelign, T., & Petros, B. (2018). Kidney stone disease: an update on current concepts. *Advances in urology*, 2018.
3. Barker, T., Boon, M., & Jones, F. (2020). The role of zinc ions in calcium oxalate monohydrate crystallization. *Journal of Crystal Growth*, 546, 125777.
4. Caruso, S., Valenti, C., Marinucci, L., Di Pasquale, F., Truppa, C., Di Benedetto, G., ... & Pagano, S. (2024). Systematic Review of Zinc's Benefits and Biological Effects on Oral Health. *Materials*, 17(4), 800.
5. Chauhan, C. K., Joseph, K. C., Parekh, B. B., & Joshi, M. J. (2008). Growth and characterization of struvite crystals.
6. Das, P., Gupta, G., Velu, V., Awasthi, R., Dua, K., & Malipeddi, H. (2017). Formation of struvite urinary stones and approaches towards the inhibition—A review. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 96, 361-370.
7. Flannigan, R., Choy, W. H., Chew, B., & Lange, D. (2014). Renal struvite stones—pathogenesis, microbiology, and management strategies. *Nature reviews Urology*, 11(6), 333-341.
8. Hutnik, N., Stanclik, A., Piotrowski, K., & Matynia, A. (2020). Effect of Copper and Zinc Ions on Struvite Nucleation and Crystal Growth Kinetics in Various Process Environments. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 29(3).
9. Indhumathi, B., & Venkatachalam, P. (2019). Effect of Euphorbia hirta root extract on struvite crystals. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 8(4), 2145-2151.
10. Kiouri, D. P., Tsoupra, E., Peana, M., Perlepes, S. P., Stefanidou, M. E., & Chasapis, C. T. (2023). Multifunctional role of zinc in human health: an update. *EXCLI journal*, 22, 809.
11. Lu, X., Huang, Z., Liang, Z., Li, Z., Yang, J., Wang, Y., & Wang, F. (2021). Co-precipitation of Cu and Zn in precipitation of struvite. *Science of The Total Environment*, 764, 144269.
12. Manzoor, M. A., Singh, B., Agrawal, A. K., Arun, A. B., Mujeeburahiman, M., & Rekha, P. D. (2018). Morphological and micro-tomographic study on the evolution of struvite in synthetic urine infected with bacteria and investigation of its pathological biomineralization. *PLoS One*, 13(8), e0202306.
13. Mohsenpour, B., Ahmadi, A., Baneh, A. M., Hajibagheri, K., Ghaderi, E., Afrasiabian, S., & Azizi, S. (2019). Relation between serum zinc levels and recurrent urinary tract infections in female patients: A case-control study. *Medical journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, 33, 33.
14. Muryanto, S., & Bayuseno, A. P. (2014). Influence of Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ as additives on crystallization kinetics and morphology of struvite. *Powder Technology*, 253, 602-607.
15. Negri, A. L. (2018). The role of zinc in urinary stone disease. *International Urology and Nephrology*, 50, 879-883.
16. Selvaraju, R., & Bhuvaneshwari, M. (2020). Growth and Spectral Investigation on Pure Calcium Phosphate Doped With (Copper and Magnesium) Crystals.
17. Paun, S., Tudosie, M., Petris, R., & Macovei, R. (2012). The effects of zinc on human body, including on renal failure and renal transplantation. *Journal of Medicine and Life*, 5(Spec Issue), 137.
18. Polat, S., & Eral, H. B. (2022). Effect of hyaluronic acid on the struvite crystallization: A structural, morphological, and thermal analysis study. *Journal of Crystal Growth*, 592, 126734.
19. Prywer, J., Torzewska, A., & Mielniczek-Brzóska, E. (2024). Understanding the role of zinc ions on struvite nucleation and growth in the context of infection urinary stones. *Metallomics*, 16(5), mfae017.
20. Raja, F. N., Worthington, T., Isaacs, M. A., Rana, K. S., & Martin, R. A. (2019). The antimicrobial efficacy of zinc doped phosphate-based glass for treating catheter associated urinary tract infections. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*, 103, 109868.
21. Schaffer, J. N., & Pearson, M. M. (2017). Proteus mirabilis and urinary tract infections. *Urinary tract infections: Molecular pathogenesis and clinical management*, 383-433.
22. Selvaraju, R., & Bhuvaneshwari, M. (2020). Growth and Spectral Investigation on Pure Calcium Phosphate Doped With (Copper and Magnesium) Crystals.
23. Singh, V. K., & Rai, P. K. (2014). Kidney stone analysis techniques and the role of major and trace elements on their pathogenesis: a review. *Biophysical reviews*, 6(3), 291-310.
24. Suryawanshi, V. B. (2021, September). Effect of zinc ions on the crystallization of urinary struvite-K crystals. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2369, No. 1). AIP Publishing
25. Vasuki, R., & Selvaraju, R. (2019). Growth and Spectral studies on Gel technique struvite crystals.
26. Zhang, C., Xu, K., Zheng, M., Li, J., & Wang, C. (2018). Factors affecting the crystal size of struvite-K formed in synthetic urine using a stirred reactor. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 57(50), 17301-17309.